

IMPROVING ADAPTIVE MANUFACTURING PROCESS FLOW PERFORMANCE USING INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY

Adel Muhsin Elewe

Project and construction department, Mustansiriyah University, Iraq

Email: adelmuhsin@uomustansiriyah.edu.iq

Rana M. Al-Salman

Collage of science, Mustansiriyah University, Iraq

Email: ranawee2003@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Smart manufacturing is a design of production system that combines the product information with the internet of things based on wireless connection to improve productivity. The essential factor in developing the flow of material in smart manufacturing is the facility layout design. For that, the present article developed a new method to improve productivity. Various IT software packages are available in the market specifically designed for the manufacturing sector to cater to diverse manufacturing needs and requirements. The primary investigation assessed the impact of implementing risk management techniques on performance indicators by utilizing a combination of surveys, expert opinions, interviews, and exploratory research, drawing upon previous studies in the field of manufacturing. Due to the condensed nature of the user's content, it is not feasible to restructure it into an academic manner. The initial findings were obtained by calculating the average risk assessment. The identification of the relative importance index RII effect facilitated the determination of the consequences. The results of the results indicate a high level of resistance to change and a moderate level of effectiveness in scheduling and Information and Communication Technology based job planning, with scores The factors are the communication procedure, IT security expertise workflow for engineers and the impact of electronic communication. The MCDA results yielded outcomes that were both more accurate and practical.

Keywords:MCDA, manufacturing risk factors, ICT

INTRODUCTION

Information technology (IT) refers to the range of equipment and methods that can store, retrieve, transport, and modify data. This expression pertains to the utilization of information and communication technologies (ICT) within the manufacturing sector for the purposes of manufacturing management, planning, and execution, as well as for the integration of ICT into the final product. The information and communication technology sector has witnessed significant and groundbreaking breakthroughs across all disciplines. Various factors impact the implementation of ICT [1]. Currently, it is widely recognized that the utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) enhances the competitiveness of companies [2]. In this context, the term "distraction" refers to how information and communication technology (ICT) prevents individuals from focusing on their tasks, hence affecting their performance in manufacturing and at work. An excessive reliance on ICTs as a substitute for face-to-face contact might be a potential cause of disruption. ICT introduces "interference," or elements that impede clear communication, into the process of planning and managing manufacturing efforts [3]. Despite potential deficiencies in the quality of manufacturing product data, the final revenue and expenditure accounting can yield dependable data. Traditional control systems suffer from both delayed information transmission and insufficiently detailed data, making it difficult to make informed regulatory and planning decisions. Multiple writers have presented specific facts about the swift integration of information and communication technologies (ICT) in the industrial sector over the last two decades, particularly by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). As a result, the management of the site and other production-related activities have not changed significantly, even though most information and communication technology solutions in the manufacturing industry are used for supporting operations. It is worth mentioning that 90% of the expenditures on information and communication technology are allocated to the technical work center or central office, whereas only 10% are allocated to the field [4].

The primary goal of this research is to discover and improve the approaches currently used for model manufacturing and analysis. The crucial task is to ascertain if the present techniques are enough for constructing intricate formations utilizing ICT. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to conduct research on the complex manufacturing components used to assess their efficacy, as well as develop a decision-making model that can evaluate the importance of various impacts of information and communication technology (ICT).

ICT strategy in manufacturing

The notion of strategic alignment arises from the necessity to integrate information and communication technology infrastructure with strategic endeavors in order to enhance ICT utilization and provide a competitive advantage for the firm or corporate strategy [5]. According to Alaloul et al. (2019), it is recommended that the industrial sector should implement processes related to the Fourth Industrial Revolution. They contended that despite the presence of these technologies, substantial disparities persist. By implementing IR 4.0, the manufacturing sector has the potential to achieve the same level of productivity as other industries such as transportation and production [6]. Next, we utilize the Rational Hierarchy Process, which involves training the weights of criteria and using a fuzzy technique to determine the rank of candidates based on their proximity to the best possible solution. This allows us to arrange the candidates in a hierarchical manner. The conclusions of the scenario analysis are considered satisfactory [7]. This article focuses on the assessment of construction manufacturing. Thus, it is crucial to consider the performance of manufacturing schemes as a problem with several criteria that may be resolved using a decision-making technique that takes into account multiple standards. Results have been conveyed using M-TOPSIS due to the possibility of civil manufacturing activities being conducted in a more relaxed manner rather than intentionally. Assessing the quality of a well-constructed manufacturing is a difficult task since the success of a manufacturing relies on achieving goals across several linked criteria [8]. The average risk of delay for industrial manufacturing in Ethiopia is 38%, indicating a high level of hazard. This effort aims to help contribution managers mitigate the risks associated with schedule cancellations and delays by careful planning and strategic adjustments [9]. The outcomes of two separate manufacturing exhibit substantial progress towards the general goals of the system, facilitating the manufacturing' faster, more cost-effective, and more reliable completion. Due to the increased significance of cost, the price of each action is decreased in descending order from the most expensive to the least expensive. Eleweet al.[10,11] developed an innovative method to address challenging situations by modifying the Firefly algorithm and including a scanning strategy. The MC-GPSO method was devised by Talib et al. [12] and bin Hasnan et al. [13] to tackle problems of this magnitude.

The quality becomes almost same when the duration of an activity approaches the most probable duration. This approach has the potential to create new opportunities for research and the expansion of knowledge in the field of plan design [14]. Risk allocation is a crucial process of decision-making that establishes the roles and obligations of all parties involved in a

manufacturing. This technique, designed for collaborative agreement, would guide authorities along a distribution chain to oversee the participant with the highest level of risk [15]. In order to showcase the possible use and efficiency of the upcoming method, a case study was conducted to analyze the competitiveness of contracting firms. The findings indicate that the use of grey relations practice procedures can be a valid method of decision support for tasks involving uncertain or unclear data [16]. Although lean techniques are crucial, there is a lack of comprehensive research aimed at understanding the key factors that facilitate their implementation. In addition, there are few techniques available for identifying essential components. To determine the optimal option, this study employed the significantly biased Entropy Technique for Order of Favorite by Resemblance. The last step involved conducting an empirical investigation inside Malaysia's manufacturing sector to implement this approach. The number 17. Many developing countries want to undertake the construction of intricate architectural manufacturings that serve both commercial and leisure reasons. It is important to acknowledge and evaluate the risks associated with these manufacturing, notwithstanding the potential high expense of implementing them [18].

Manufacturing flow factors

Process flows provide a systematic framework for manufacturing at each stage of a product's life cycle, starting from its inception and ending with its completion. A process flow is beneficial for manufacturing engineers since it provides a clear and standardized overview of the resources needed at each stage. The flow of a system refers to the movement of labor inside it. The distinction between "good" flow and "bad" flow lies in the former representing a consistent and predictable pattern of movement, while the latter refers to the start and end of a work. Each instance of flow interruption raises the probability of trash accumulation. The production flow consists of seven steps:

1. The movement of raw materials
2. The reciprocal flow of work-in-process
3. The transportation of finished goods
- 4- The flow of the operators
- 5- The motion of the equipment

6. The communication procedure

7-Workflow for engineers

Businesses that have mastered adaptive manufacturing have a considerably higher chance of producing finished goods and services with fewer defects when all seven of these channels are operating in unison. Maintaining production in this manner also results in cost savings for the business. Optimizing profits is closely linked to streamlining procedures to boost overall efficiency. Here are just a few of the numerous ways a company using lean manufacturing techniques might set itself apart from competitors [19,20].

ICT factors

Information and communication technology (ICT) refers to a b range of instruments and resources used for transmitting, storing, creating, sharing, or exchanging data.

1. Procurement and invoicing utilizing (ICT)
2. Utilizing ICT for scheduling and organizing.
3. IT security expertise
4. Information-based resource management
5. Utilizing information and communication technology for labor control
6. Information-driven material management
7. Technology-supported equipment control
8. The Impact of Electronic Communication

"Information and communications technology" (ICT) encompasses all hardware and software used in networking, according to its most comprehensive definition. Information technology (IT) encompasses the combination of hardware, software, and methodologies used to manage data processing, which includes storage, retrieval, and access. ICT, short for Information and Communication Technology, encompasses telecommunications-based technologies that provide

access to information. This encompasses a wide range of technologies, including wireless networks, mobile phones, the Internet, and other electronic communication techniques [21].

METHOD AND MATERIAL

RELATIVE IMPORTANT INDEX (RII)

The evaluation of risk factor management should consider the quantity and severity of the expenditure, as well as the risk tolerance of decision-makers and other pertinent factors. As a result, the extent of authority must be determined after the hazards have been evaluated. The decision-maker's willingness to communicate is contingent upon the level of risk that the client, the community, or the individual is willing to assume. It is essential to establish an acceptable level of risk in order to make informed decisions regarding the timeline, budget, technical solutions, and manufacturing procedures. The permissible risk factor may be established at the outset of an undertaking, which facilitates the making of more well-informed decisions. A precise threshold for acceptable risk should be established in the manufacturing's risk considerations policy [22]. A situation may or may not be acceptable, contingent upon the decision-maker's capacity and desire to identify and mitigate relevant hazards. The adoption of risk factors is influenced by decision criteria, past knowledge and experience with comparable choice scenarios, and the perception of risk factors by individuals or organizations. The certainty equivalent, which is the guaranteed or anticipated value of assets associated with a hazardous circumstance, is the foundation of all of them. The RII test was implemented by the source to ascertain the extent to which survey responses were influenced by risk factors. This was facilitated by the precise numerical representation of the risk level for each variable [23]. The objective of this investigation was to determine the RII by employing the subsequent formula.

$$RII = \sum (P_i U_i) / Nn$$

RII = relative importance index

P_i = respondent's rating of risk factors

U_i = number of respondents placing identical weighting/rating on the factor

N = sample size people responded to the survey

n = the highest attainable score for each factor

MCDA Method

MCDA, short for Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis, is a systematic approach used to make informed conclusions by taking into account several criteria. A Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) technique often yields a limited number of choices, each characterized by a unique combination of criteria. To assess each option, we may calculate several ratios that reflect various factors for choosing. By multiplying these ratios, it becomes possible to make comparisons. Each criterion is allocated a weight according to its proportion. Utilizing relative values instead of absolute ones is a notable advantage of this approach. The subsequent numerical example offers a clear and comprehensible illustration of the computations involved in this technique. We utilize identical numerical values for our dataset as the numerical illustration of the weighted sum model.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Developing manufacturing process have substantial obstacles in effectively managing manufacturing risks throughout implementation. This company strategy seeks to optimize financial gains while simultaneously generating positive social, environmental, and political impacts. The primary goal of sustainability risk management is to achieve a compromise between increasing benefits and minimizing downsides. The dangers described in this article have the potential to significantly disrupt or completely halt manufacturing operations in Iraq. This strategy mitigates the likelihood of supply chain interruptions caused by occurrences such as labor disputes or natural disasters. Prior to examining hazards in further detail, it is important to complete the average risk assessment. Firstly, ascertain the numerical measure of the standard deviation. Prior to engaging in statistical analysis or data interpretation, it is crucial to comprehend the variability inherent in the dataset. This tool can enhance people's comprehension of patterns, outliers, reliability, dataset comparability, and other related considerations. The main advantage of the standard deviation is its reliable and consistent calculability. Standard deviation enables the possibility of doing statistical and mathematical study. Table 1 displays the standard deviations (STDs) for the variables.

Table 1: STD results

THE MANUFACTURING FLOW FACTOR	STD	THE ICT FACTOR	STD
The movement of raw materials	0.522	Procurement and invoicing utilizing ICT	0.208
The reciprocal flow of work-in-process	1.213	Utilizing ICT for scheduling and organizing.	0.240
The transportation of finished goods	0.565	IT security expertise	0.337
The flow of the operators	1.263	Information-based resource management	0.212
The motion of the equipment	0.311	Utilizing ICT for labor control	0.519
The communication procedure	0.028	Information-driven material management	0.212
Workflow for engineers	0.721	Technology-supported equipment control	0.519
		The Impact of Electronic Communication	1.078

The next step is to look at the pertinent risk factors. The variables' ranking criteria provide insight into how to assess the risk factors based on the potential risks they represent. Technology adoption, the existence of risk material, and other significant factors may have an effect on ranking factors. A deep understanding of ranking factors is necessary for efficient factor optimization. A simplified process is needed to assess the possible risks presented by third parties. It is simply unrealistic to expect the risk rating technique of a compliance program to account for every possible scenario. Though there could be more factors, these two are most

likely the most significant and reliable ones. Table 2 display the risk factors used in this investigation along with their RII rankings.

Table 2: results of RII method

THE MANUFACTURING FLOW FACTOR	RII	THE ICT FACTOR	RII
The movement of raw materials	0.812	Procurement and invoicing utilizing ICT	0.842
The reciprocal flow of work-in-process	0.428	Utilizing ICT for scheduling and organizing.	0.822
The transportation of finished goods	0.796	IT security expertise	0.862
The flow of the operators	0.398	Information-based resource management	0.82
The motion of the equipment	0.83	Utilizing ICT for labor control	0.768
The communication procedure	0.89	Information-driven material management	0.82
Workflow for engineers	0.638	Technology-supported equipment control	0.768
		The Impact of Electronic Communication	0.59

The results observed two effective factors. The factors are The communication procedure(0.89) and IT security expertise (0.862). In order to investigate the accurate risk factors, the MCDA present another opinion. Table 3 resents another effective factors.

Table 3: results of MCDA factors

THE MANUFACTURING FLOW FACTOR	MCDA	THE ICT FACTOR	MCDA
The movement of raw materials	0.386	Procurement and invoicing utilizing ICT	0.2433
The reciprocal flow of	0.407	Utilizing ICT for	0.236

work-in-process		scheduling and organizing.	
The transportation of finished goods	0.398	IT security expertise	0.393
The flow of the operators	0.391	Information-based resource management	0.237
The motion of the equipment	0.243	Utilizing ICT for labor control	0.424
The communication procedure	0.315	Information-driven material management	0.237
Workflow for engineers	0.427	Technology-supported equipment control	0.424
		The Impact of Electronic Communication	0.592

Workflow for engineers 0.427 and the impact of Electronic Communication 0.592 represent more accurate risk factors. The results observed more reasonable risk factors.

CONCLUSION

The industrial sector in Iraq has a long-standing record of neglecting financial constraints and risk management protocols. Researchers have extensively investigated the origins of industrial hazards over an extended period. The existing literature lacks comprehensive information about the benefits and drawbacks of different solutions and their effects on manufacturing firms' operations, competitiveness, alignment, and deviation from strategy growth. To understand the root causes of different events and recognize the significance of including risk factors in decision-making, it is necessary to analyze this connection and evaluate the possible hazards involved. Efficiently overseeing day-to-day activities is crucial for a business's efforts to evaluate and mitigate risks. The main investigation analyzed the impact of surveys, expert comments, interviews, and exploratory research on performance indicators after the adoption of risk management techniques. It accomplished this by utilizing previous studies on manufacturing. Converting the user's input into an academic style is not feasible due to its extremely compact nature. The initial set of findings was derived by calculating the average of the risk assessments. The components include the communication style (0.89) and competence with information

technology security (0.862). The MCDA technique found two different risk variables: the engineers' workflow (0.427) and the influence of electronic communication (0.592). The outcomes of Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) revealed a more pragmatic and authentic approach.

Acknowledgments: the author wish to thanks Department of construction, Mustansiriyah University, for supporting this work.

References

- [1] I. Computing and I. Technology, “3 . Information Technologies applications for Manufacturing,” pp. 37–46, 2000.
- [2] T. D. Moshood, G. Nawanir, S. Sorooshian, F. Mahmud, and A. Q. Adeleke, “Barriers and benefits of ICT adoption in the Nigerian manufacturing industry. A comprehensive literature review,” *Appl. Syst. Innov.*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 1–19, 2020, doi: 10.3390/asi3040046.
- [3] A. Rimmington, G. Dickens, and C. Pasquire, “Impact of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) on manufacturingmanufacturings,” *Organ. Technol. Manag. Constr. An Int. J.*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1367–1382, 2015, doi: 10.5592/otmcj.2015.3.4.
- [4] P. Orihuela, J. Orihuela, and S. Pacheco, “Information and Communications Technology in Manufacturing: A Proposal for Production Control,” *Procedia Eng.*, vol. 164, no. June, pp. 150–157, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.proeng.2016.11.604.
- [5] H. K. Eliwa, M. B. Jelodar, and M. Poshdar, “Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Utilization and Infrastructure Alignment in Manufacturing Organizations,” *s*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 1–19, 2022, doi: 10.3390/s12030281.
- [6] W. S. Alaloul, M. S. Liew, N. A. W. A. Zawawi, and I. B. Kennedy, “Industrial Revolution 4.0 in the manufacturing industry: Challenges and opportunities for stakeholders,” *Ain Shams Eng. J.*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 225–230, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.asej.2019.08.010.
- [7] F. Torfi and A. Rashidi, “Selection of manufacturing managers in manufacturing Firms using analytic hierarchy process (AHP) and fuzzy Topsis: A case study,” *J. Constr. Dev. Ctries.*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 69–89, 2011.

- [8] U. Pinter and I. Pšunder, "Evaluating manufacturing success with use of the M-TOPSIS method," *J. Civ. Eng. Manag.*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 16–23, 2013, doi: 10.3846/13923730.2012.734849.
- [9] T. Gebrehiwet and H. Luo, "Risk level evaluation on manufacturing lifecycle using fuzzy comprehensive evaluation and TOPSIS," *Symmetry (Basel)*, vol. 11, no. 1, 2019, doi: 10.3390/sym11010012.
- [10] Elewe, Adel Muhsin, K. Bin Hasnan, and A. Bin Nawawi. "Hybridized firefly algorithm for multi-objective radio frequency identification (RFID) network planning." *ARPN J Eng Appl Sci* 12, no. 3 (2017): 834-840.
- [11] Abdullah, H., N. H. Talib, A. M. Elewe, S. Tahir, and I. Campus. "An efficient algorithm for largescale RFID network planning." no. September (2019).
- [12] Talib, Nihad Hasan, Khalid Bin Hasnan, Azli Bin Nawawi, Haslina Binti Abdullah, and Adel Muhsin Elewe. "Monitoring large-scale rail transit systems based on an analytic hierarchy process/gradient-based cuckoo search algorithm (GBCS) scheme." *Urban Rail Transit* 6, no. 2 (2020): 132-144.
- [13] bin Hasnan, Khalid, Adel Muhsin Elewe, Azli bin Nawawi, and Suhaidah Tahir. "Comparative evaluation of firefly algorithm and MC-GPSO for optimal RFID network planning." In 2017 8th international conference on information technology (ICIT), pp. 70-74. IEEE, 2017.
- [14] S. A. Banihashemi, M. Khalilzadeh, J. Antucheviciene, and J. Šaparauskas, "Trading off time–cost–quality in manufacturing scheduling problems with fuzzy SWARA–TOPSIS approach," *s*, vol. 11, no. 9, 2021, doi: 10.3390/s11090387.
- [15] G. Khazaeni, M. Khanzadi, and A. Afshar, "Optimum risk allocation model for manufacturing contracts: Fuzzy TOPSIS approach," *Can. J. Civ. Eng.*, vol. 39, no. 7, pp. 789–800, 2012, doi: 10.1139/L2012-038.
- [16] E. K. Zavadskas, T. Vilutiene, Z. Turskis, and J. Tamosaitiene, "Contractor selection for manufacturing works by applying saw-g and topsis grey techniques," *J. Bus. Econ. Manag.*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 34–55, 2010, doi: 10.3846/jbem.2010.03.
- [17] G. Dehdasht, M. Salim Ferwati, R. M. Zin, and N. Z. Abidin, *A hybrid approach using*

- entropy and TOPSIS to select key drivers for a successful and sustainable lean manufacturing implementation*, vol. 15, no. 2. 2020. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0228746.
- [18] J. Tamošaitienė, M. Khosravi, M. Cristofaro, D. W. M. Chan, and H. Sarvari, "Identification and prioritization of critical risk factors of commercial and recreational complex manufacturings: A delphi study using the topsis method," *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 11, no. 17, pp. 1–24, 2021, doi: 10.3390/app11177906.
- [19] Tan, Q., Liu, Y., Fan, Z., Zhang, J., Yin, Y. and Zhang, M.X., 2020. Effect of processing parameters on the densification of an additively manufactured 2024 Al alloy. *Journal of Materials Science & Technology*, 58, pp.34-45.
- [20] Gairola, S., Singh, G., Jayaganthan, R. and Ajay, J., 2023. High temperature performance of additively manufactured Al 2024 alloy: Constitutive modelling, dynamic recrystallization evolution and kinetics. *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, 25, pp.3425-3443.
- [21] N. Sunke and F. Schultmann, "Requirements for sustainable manufacturing materials and components," *Conf. Proc. CIB W115 Constr. Mater. Steward. Lifecycle Des. Build. Syst. Mater.*, pp. 24–28, 2009.
- [22] O. M. Shehatto, "Cost estimation for manufacturingmanufacturings in Gaza Strip using Artificial Neural Network (ANN)," *CE-Unit cost*, no. June, p. 102, 2013.
- [23] H. Supriyono and C. P. Sari, "Developing decision support systems using the weighted product method for house selection," *AIP Conf. Proc.*, vol. 1977, 2018, doi: 10.1063/1.5042905.